

A next generation library of AI-based data-driven services for the built environment

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Abstract—Nowadays, buildings account for almost 40% of the overall energy consumption. Thus, it is essential to involve a broad range of stakeholders throughout the building lifecycle, with the development of innovative, cross-cutting energy services, which exploit the ever-increasing volume of available data. In this paper we present a novel library of AI-based data-driven services for the built environment with the aim of addressing decarbonization challenges and of facilitating data-driven decision making. The issue of handling energy-related data in an efficient way is tackled, incorporating them in user-friendly, micro-services oriented technological components. The architecture of this AI-base library is thoroughly presented covering learning, optimization and simulation tasks. showcase our approach to energy resource management.

Index Terms—Energy Management; Artificial Intelligence; Decision Support; Intelligent Systems; Buildings

I. INTRODUCTION

The European Union’s (EU) buildings account for almost 40% of its energy consumption. Thus, reducing the energy density of the building sector is a key component of any effective climate policy. Unfortunately, only 3% of the EU’s building stock is considered energy efficient, and 97% of the buildings are not [1]. With a low construction rate and low demolition and renovation rates [2], the majority of the EU’s current building stock, which was mostly built before 1990, will still be in use in 2050 [3]. In order to tackle this issue, it is imperative for the EU to prioritize deep renovations that can achieve savings of 60% or more [22], as well as to accelerate the rate of retrofitting to more than 2% per year to improve building performance and reduce pressure on

energy grids. Evidence-based decision support is necessary for making informed retrofitting decisions [4], [5].

In addition to the previously discussed challenges, it’s important to note that the increasing use of advanced Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), like the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT)/Blockchain, and Big Data, is leading to a surge in data generated within buildings [6]–[8]. This is driving the shift towards a smart building landscape impacting every aspect of the built environment, from how individuals and businesses use and interact with properties to how building energy consumption and construction details are recorded and analyzed [9]. By utilizing data to inform decision-making and implementing digital upgrades like Energy Conservation Measures (ECMs), operational efficiencies can be improved at a low cost.

Having set the above-mentioned technological challenges and in order to achieve the pre-defined ambitious energy and environmental goals for a climate-neutral building stock, it is essential to involve a broad range of stakeholders throughout the building lifecycle, from design and construction to refurbishment and demolition [10]. This will ensure that the transition to low-carbon and sustainable living is both feasible and embraced by all, ensuring that the built environment can break free from current silo thinking. In this respect, traditional silo practices, where stakeholders manage their own data, can be replaced by digital and smart buildings that bring together diverse data sources and put stakeholders at the center [11], [12]. The proposed library of data-driven services

can drive this transformation by leveraging heterogeneous data and advanced digital building services to promote trust, transparency, and informed decision-making.

The starting pillar of this set of data-driven services is trust and transparency as, sharing data leads to potential development of new services that benefit multiple stakeholders and industries related to the building sector [13]. These services could improve building infrastructure planning and investment decisions through a comprehensive understanding of factors such as energy, climate, economics, user behaviour, and regulations. However, working with cross-domain data requires a clear understanding of its nature and the use of advanced digital technologies like IoT, AI, cloud, and big data to efficiently process large amounts of data quickly and securely [14].

In this paper we present a novel library of AI-based data-driven services for the built environment with the aim of addressing the above-mentioned challenges and facilitate data-driven decision making. This study addresses the issue of handling energy-related data in an efficient way, incorporating them in user-friendly, micro-services oriented technological components, while at the same time following a solid methodological approach for each micro-service.

Apart from this introductory section, the rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II provides an overview of the holistic architecture for buildings' analytics services. Section III introduces the catalogue of AI-based analytics services split into three clusters. Section IV presents a real-life case-study using the presented AI library for predicting the energy consumption of a building in Greece. Finally, in Section IV the main conclusions of the paper are summarized and key points for further research are proposed.

II. A HOLISTIC ARCHITECTURE FOR BUILDINGS' ANALYTICS SERVICES

AI-based data-driven services have emerged as a critical component in the contemporary built environment. The proposed multilayered architecture provides a holistic approach on how to set up such services that utilize AI technologies to deliver data-driven solutions tailored to the needs of building occupants and energy stakeholders. These services rely on the collection and analysis of data from various sources, including sensors, building management systems, and other internet of things (IoT) devices. This represents the initial layer of the architecture, named as the Data Serving Layer. The subsequent layer is the Intelligence Layer, where the data is processed and analysed using machine learning algorithms to generate actionable insights that can improve the efficiency of buildings and enhance occupant comfort. These services range from machine learning-based approaches that use data analysis to optimize building performance, to optimization-based methods that use mathematical and optimisation algorithms to find the best solution for a given set of constraints, to simulation-based services that use computer models to predict building performance, to multi-criteria decision making (MCDA) - based services that evaluate different energy-saving options

based on multiple criteria. The criteria established for this problem involve predicted values of total load, losses, renewables, and hydro as provided by a transmission system operator, as well as the value of total building and on-site PV consumption, if applicable. The outcomes of these have two ultimate recipients: the interface layer, which consists of personalised graphical user interfaces designed for service delivery, and the Digital Twins. Digital twins, as described in [15], are dynamic and self-evolving virtual models that accurately represent the current state of their physical counterparts. To harness the output of AI-based data-driven services, Digital Twins rely on the Serving Layer. This layer facilitates direct communication with the Digital Twins or immediate access through the Artifacts Layer, where the generated AI-based and data-driven models are stored. Across all of these layers, the security of communication is upheld through Identity Access Management Layer, which is accountable for managing user identities and roles within the broader ecosystem. The overall architecture of the proposed framework is presented in Figure 1.

The input of these services is provided by a Business Intelligence Layer which is responsible for fetching data (dynamic, static data and data marts) to the AI services. However, the process of collecting, pre-processing and fetching the data does not fall within the scope of this paper. The services have been clustered into 4 different categories according to their nature and to the methods and techniques employed to provide results. Following, an overview of these four categories of services are presented, highlighting their strengths, weaknesses, and potential applications

- **Learning-based services** for energy and buildings use advanced machine learning algorithms to analyze data and improve building performance. This includes predicting energy consumption patterns, optimizing building control systems, and detecting anomalies in energy use. For example, a learning-based service might use historical energy usage data to train a model that predicts future energy consumption, allowing building owners and operators to identify areas where energy savings can be achieved. This approach can also be used to optimize building control systems, such as HVAC systems, by using machine learning algorithms to determine the most energy-efficient settings based on real-time conditions.
- **Optimization-based services** for energy and buildings use mathematical algorithms to find the best solution for a given set of constraints. This includes optimizing energy consumption while maintaining comfort levels, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and minimizing costs. For example, an optimization-based service might use linear programming algorithms to determine the most cost-effective combination of energy-saving measures for a building. This approach can also be used to optimize energy production in renewable energy systems, such as photovoltaic arrays, by determining the optimal combination of equipment and settings to maximize energy

Fig. 1: The architectural scheme of the AI-based library.

production.

- **Simulation-based services** for energy and buildings use computer models to predict how a building will perform in various scenarios. This allows building owners and operators to make informed decisions about energy use and retrofit options. For example, a simulation-based service might use building energy simulation software to predict how a building will perform after a retrofit, including changes in energy consumption, indoor environmental quality, and thermal comfort. This information can be used to evaluate the potential energy savings, environmental impact, and return on investment of different retrofit options.
- **Multicriteria Decision Making (MCDA) - based services** for energy and buildings use MCDA methods to evaluate and compare different energy-saving options based on multiple, often conflicting, criteria [16]. This

includes cost, environmental impact, technical feasibility, and other factors that may be relevant to a specific building or project. For example, an MCDA-based service might use a decision-making method, such as Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) [17], to compare the potential energy savings and costs of different retrofit options. This approach can provide building owners and operators with a comprehensive evaluation of different options, taking into account multiple criteria, and allowing them to make well-informed decisions about energy-saving investments.

The final aspect to consider is related to the output of the developed analytics services. In certain cases, the results of these services may be accessible via web-based applications or APIs. However, there are other instances where the output of analytics services can serve as an input to more sophisticated systems, such as building digital twins [18]. Building digital twins can be perceived as virtual replicas of physical buildings

that integrate data from various sources, including energy and building analytics, to provide real-time insights into the building's performance and operations. By incorporating the output of analytics services, digital twins can simulate and optimize the building's energy usage, identify inefficiencies and maintenance needs, and facilitate informed decision-making for improvements. This integration of analytics services into digital twins offers building operators and energy stakeholders an informed understanding of the building's energy consumption patterns, identifying areas for improvement, and optimizing energy usage in real-time. Furthermore, this integration allows the digital twin to identify maintenance needs, optimize building systems, and support operational decisions.

III. CLUSTERS OF ANALYTICS SERVICES

Having presented the overall architecture of the proposed AI-based library, in this section the focus is laid on the description of the included services. The library consists of 15 different services which can be categorized in 5 different clusters. A schematic representation is depicted in Figure 2.

A. Building Profiling and Energy Forecasting

This cluster includes a series of forecasting algorithms which are focused on providing predictions for several energy-related topics, including the overall building's consumption, the consumption of specific sub-systems of a building (i.e. lighting, heating, cooling, ventilation), the consumption of district heating networks in terms of heating and hot water, as well as the production of several renewable energy sources like photovoltaics [19], [20].

The primary objective of the performance monitoring and benchmarking service is to offer energy predictions to effectively monitor and benchmark building energy performance. In this respect, the services under this cluster are designed to support building energy consumption reduction and detect potential malfunctions by utilizing time series data to develop machine learning models. The models use and expand the traditional ML/DL algorithms for energy forecasting, such as Random Forest Regression, Decision Trees, Support Vector Machines (SVMs) Neural Networks (ANN, CNN, LSTM, RNN), XGBoost and LightGBM models to support energy forecasting for different time horizons.

According to the previously described architecture, the services may function independently as standalone applications, in conjunction with a visualization tool [23], or by providing the requisite inputs to other services to offer more advanced functionalities, such as those focused on fault detection analysis or the comfort category. In the latter scenario, stakeholders aim to perform automated asset monitoring and maintenance, including energy consumption reduction and fault monitoring. Thus, benchmarking aspects play a pivotal role, and in certain cases, alarm systems may be necessary to ensure that any issues are promptly detected and addressed.

B. Energy Resources Management

Within this cluster, data-driven services are developed that concentrate on the efficient management of electrical networks

in buildings and district heating networks (DHN). The cluster comprises data on electric usage within buildings [24], monitoring of electric vehicles (EVs) and EV chargers, and integrated monitoring of multi-node district heating networks. The data collected through these efforts will be utilised to develop six services, as shown in Figure 2, with the aim of proactively detecting faults and reducing operational costs, energy consumption, and carbon footprint across these networks.

Beginning with an analysis of predictive maintenance and fault detection, the widespread use of smart sensors and intelligent buildings empowers load management to enhance energy efficiency. Data-driven solutions play a crucial role in enabling real-time fault detection and prediction, resulting in reduced annual maintenance expenses. By continuously monitoring sensor data and employing rule-based algorithms, the system will generate relevant recommendations and alerts, effectively functioning as a Decision Support System (DSS). Ultimately, the DSS will propose a compensation strategy to the Facility Manager.

With the objective of network optimization and optimal resource management, several services and corresponding methodologies have been defined to attain this aim. The first focuses on the economic optimization of district network production by establishing ML-based simulation environments. The objective is to manage optimization strategies related to district heating and reduce operating costs through the optimal utilization of renewable energy sources. The remaining services focus on the management of flexible loads, such as EVs. These services aim to optimize energy resource management while simultaneously reducing the carbon footprint of the networks. Optimization algorithms, such as genetic algorithms and particle swarm optimization, along with multicriteria decision analysis techniques, will be utilized. These approaches will be applied across various time horizons, including real-time and future scenarios, as well as different network configurations, such as single building electricity network management, cluster of buildings electricity network management, and EV fleet management. The expected outcome of these services is the generation of insights, schedules, and alerts for the optimal management of the aforementioned networks.

C. Thermal Comfort and People Well-being

The services that fall into this cluster aim at defining and creating data-driven models capable of measuring and quantifying human thermal comfort, while at the same time ensuring a proper balance of the other quantities that contribute to the IEQ (visual, acoustic comfort, and indoor air quality) and to energy consumption. Thus, starting from existing buildings' data and streaming data collected via the buildings' available infrastructure, the aim of these services are to provide notifications of the occupants' community to the smart grid 'welfare', comfort/preferences optimisation based on self-learning of individual and collective-level preferences, intelligent scheduling of smart home/building appliance to better manage the contracted power while matching end-user habits and preferences [25].

Fig. 2: The 5 clusters of analytics services.

Moreover, a specific service is devoted to the development of comfort performance contracts. The comfort performance contract is a relatively new term which addressed the problem of improving the comfort of building occupants while minimizing energy consumption. This term is a variation of the traditional energy performance contracts which solely focus on energy savings neglecting the occupants comfort aspect. The contractor responsible for implementing this contract is obligated to meet the agreed-upon comfort standards, such as indoor air quality, temperature, and lighting levels, while also reducing energy consumption, or even he is responsible for maintaining and monitoring the building systems to ensure optimal performance. The application of such comfort contracts could bring several benefits, including improved occupant satisfaction and productivity, reduced energy consumption, and reduced environmental impact.

D. Renovation Roadmaps and Energy Efficiency Financing

Through this cluster of services, the objective is to enhance energy efficiency and encourage effective renovation initiatives to improve the demand and information regarding potential energy efficiency interventions in the building sector [26].

To facilitate energy efficiency financing and policy-making, the Dynamic high-Resolution demand-side Management (DREEM) [27] model will be employed. This model assesses the building's performance and proposes solutions

for improved energy management, with the goal of achieving long-term energy savings, reducing energy poverty, and utilizing intelligent algorithms and analytical techniques. Simultaneously, a comprehensive one-stop-shop is being developed to evaluate potential upgrade actions for energy efficiency in buildings. The platform specifically evaluates the benefits of these actions from energy, economic, environmental, and social perspectives. This approach aims to raise awareness among building owners and managers about energy efficiency actions, provide the necessary information and tools for informed decision-making, and grant access to national and local-level financial programs and incentives for energy efficiency upgrades.

E. Efficient and Climate Resilient Buildings

The final cluster of services includes the dimension of climate resiliency in buildings. Efficient and climate-resilient buildings are indispensable in mitigating energy consumption, carbon emissions, and enhancing resilience against climate change impacts. As the characteristic of each approach are highly linked to its usability and transparency, and taking into consideration the trade-offs between the accuracy of the approaches and the ease of use, the European Commission proposes some practices for resilience rating. Thus, this service aims to provide a novel indexing methodology for assessing the resilience of a building to several climate factors.

The initial stage of the climate resilience assessment for a building involves preparing a climate vulnerability and risk assessment (CVRA) methodology for the reference building. To achieve this, it is essential to evaluate the building’s exposure to each of the hazards outlined above, both current and future. Subsequently, this information can be utilized to assign appropriate weights to the technical features of the building, which are considered in the overall climate resilience assessment of the reference building. The CVRA can be conducted in two ways: either through a questionnaire or using weather data. The outcome of the CVRA is the qualitative evaluation of the building’s exposure to various climate hazards, categorized as ‘No’, ‘Very Low’, ‘Low’, ‘Moderate’, ‘High’, and ‘Very High’. The purpose of the CVRA result is to determine the weights for rating the building. To facilitate this calculation, the qualitative ratings must be converted into quantitative ratings. The next step involves identifying the characteristics of the building infrastructure of the reference building and evaluating the resilience they provide against specific climate hazards. The features of the buildings can be categorised into the building’s structural characteristics, energy systems, water management systems, sustainability practices, and crisis management systems (in the case of workplaces and large buildings).

By combining the aforementioned data and applying the necessary calculations, a comprehensive climate resilience index is derived, taking into account the building’s exposure to the considered climate hazards. Assessing climate resilience based on various climate hazards and characteristics allows for the generation of advanced outcomes. These outcomes include identifying areas where the building’s resilience is lacking against specific hazards, as well as pinpointing areas of the building that have potential for improvement.

IV. REAL-LIFE DEMONSTRATION

In this section, we will provide a detailed demonstration to illustrate the implementation of an instance of the methodologies that are under development within the context of energy resource management. This analysis will cover the available data, the methodological framework, the output, and how they can be utilized by individual services within the same cluster. The ultimate objective is to enhance informed decision-making and provide appropriate recommendations to electric vehicle users through a range of services.

The demonstration begins with the power recharging management service. To implement this, data is gathered from the total consumption measurement sensors of the reference building, as well as the provider’s billing policy (whether it is a night tariff or not), and data from the transmission system operator. In the case of data from the transmission system of Greece, the operator generates the forecasts internally and provides access to them through an application programming interface (API) request. Regarding the building consumption data, forecasts will be obtained from the cluster responsible for energy forecasting (III-A), where dedicated AI models are developed to generate them. These forecasts will also be

accessible through API requests. The objective of this service is to evaluate the carbon footprint for each hour of the 24-hour period in the following day. This evaluation is based on two methodologies that utilize multi-criteria decision analysis. The first methodology involves the use of the VIKOR method [28], which employs predicted values for the next day to evaluate the carbon footprint for each hour. Figure 3 illustrates initial results obtained by applying this method to the pilot and transmission system operator data for 30/04/2023. Based on the available data, the criteria considered in the multi-criteria method are as follows: grid load (C1), grid renewable sources (C2), grid loss (C3), building consumption (C4), and building billing energy policy (C5). The alternatives for this problem span across 24 hours a day, as this is the minimum time step of the available forecasts. It is evident that the methodology can be extended to shorter time steps, thus providing more alternatives. The weights in the method were determined using the Analytic Hierarchy Process method [30] as supplemented by experts in the energy industry. The weights for each criterion are shown in the TABLE I. The second methodology, known as Stochastic VIKOR [31], builds upon the first one by using the results of the previous 30 days to predict the carbon footprint for each hour of the following day using the Naive Bayes method [21]. The outcomes of these methods can then be used to estimate the flexibility required for effective power recharging management, as well as for other related services.

criteria	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
weights	0.22	0.09	0.18	0.43	0.08

TABLE I: Weights as calculated with the AHP method

Fig. 3: Results of standard VIKOR method.

By having an estimation of the environmental impact for each hour, these services can be leveraged by services within

the cluster, such as energy vs e-mobility package and carbon-free buildings. In energy vs e-mobility package service, this information is utilized to create an alerting and recommendation system that provides real-time monitoring of the usage of an EV charger integrated into the building's overall consumption. Through a rules system, the user will be able receive real-time assessments of charging sessions and recommendations for greener charging practices via API responses. In carbon-free buildings service, the information is utilized to evaluate multiple buildings, providing an overall cluster assessment and determining the environmental impact of consumption for each hour in each building of the cluster. In this scenario, the beneficiary has the ability to plan energy consumption among the cluster buildings, aiming to minimize the carbon footprint of the entire cluster. This ecosystem of services has been created to exchange data and interact for optimal energy resource management.

V. CONCLUSIONS

To address the efficient management of energy and non-energy related data of the building sector, this paper introduced a novel library of AI-based services tailored specifically for the built environment. The library encompasses a comprehensive range of user-friendly micro-services and technological components that streamline the handling and utilization of energy-related data. The architectural aspects of this AI-powered library are thoroughly elucidated, encompassing various tasks such as learning, optimization, and simulation. Furthermore, a practical case study from Greece was presented to demonstrate the efficacy and practical application of one of the integrated services within the library. This case study serves as a tangible example showcasing how the developed data-driven services can be employed in real-world scenarios and inter-operate to provide intelligent monitoring and management solutions.

Future research could focus on expanding the library of AI-based services. This expansion should include additional use cases from diverse geographical regions. Additionally, efforts should be directed towards refining existing services and exploring opportunities to integrate emerging technologies like blockchain or Internet of Things (IoT) to augment the overall capabilities of the library. Finally, standardization aspects are really important, in order to ensure scalability and adaptability of services for similar problems in diverse environments.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The work presented is based on research conducted within the framework of the Horizon Europe European Commission project DigiBUILD (Grant Agreement No. 101069658). The authors would like to thank all the DigiBUILD consortium partners for their fruitful discussions, remarks and observations. The content of the paper is the sole responsibility of its authors and does not necessary reflect the views of the EC.

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